

TEESSIDE UNIVERSITY

School of Computing, Engineering and Digital Technologies

Chemical Engineering

2022–2023

Hybrid Electrolysis of Seawater Using Consumable Anode

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Abstract

Fossil fuel, with a proven technology for its derivation and cheap price, is the main source of energy for the world. But this energy source is a finite resource and the by-products (CO₂) released into the environment after combustion is very detrimental. Thus communities, academia and governments have focused attention on working with renewables yet unpolluting energy source such as wind, solar etc.

But these forms of energy sources rely on nature and cannot be always provided. Yet during peak periods they can provide potent energy for various activities in our society. Thus, if this energy could be stored at these peak production periods, it can ensure the constant supply of energy in a sustainable and environmentally friendly way. There are various ways of storing this energy from primary renewable sources, yet hydrogen has received great attention.

Hydrogen undergoes combustion to produce only water as by product. It has a high energy to mass ration. Thus, it could be good for the environment and fulfil various. These are great positives for a fuel, yet the technology produce it are relatively more expensive than to produce fossil (about 3 times).

Electrolysis was chosen in this project to help the push for a non-polluting fuel, in hydrogen. In using electrolysis, sacrificial anodes in Zn, Al and Sn were used in the electrolytic setup at various voltages ranging from 1-2V to ascertain how their kinetics in producing hydrogen on a stainless-steel cathode (in all cases). Zn had a relatively fast kinetics, engendering the high production of hydrogen on the stainless-steel cathode. Al had the next best kinetics followed by Sn at laboratory temperature of about 21 degrees Celsius. Yet there was also side reaction especially in Zn and Sn anode-electrolytic setup which led to the formation precipitates around electrode. While the project dealt with short run experiment not exceeding 3 hours the implications on operation cost for scaling purposes may have to be probed further.

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1 Introduction

The risk of running out of fuel and the environmental cost associated with the usage of fossil fuel, which is the main energy source for the world (Ahn et al., 2012, Wang et al., 2021), has called for energy options to offset these drawbacks. Renewable energy such as wind, solar and hydro energy are seen as prime candidate to replace fossils. However, these energy sources rely on nature's phenomenon and thus can only be supplied in an intermittent manner. If the energies derived through these renewables could be stored, they could potentially be the energies of the future since they are clean fuel (fuels that leave no carbon footprints) and well aligned with world desired for green fuels (Du et al., 2021).

According to (Ould Amrouche et al., 2016), some of the main ways of storing renewable energy is through electrochemical cells, hydrogen and even in mechanical storage systems. But Hydrogen could be crucial in advancing the usage of renewable energies. While hydrogen has low density at ambient pressure and thus may require special storage systems, it is the fuel with the highest energy per mass. (Bičáková and Straka, 2012) suggest that hydrogen fuel can be produced through a range of raw of material but the type produced from fossil fuel accounts for about 96%; the production of hydrogen by electrolysis accounts for very small portion of hydrogen produced worldwide.

The splitting of water into components of water by electrochemical means, generally known as electrolysis of water, is one way of obtaining hydrogen. The hydrogen produced through electrolysis very pure and can be used in PEM fuel cell applications. Depending on the chemicals for increasing the conductivity of the water (acid or base) used in electrochemical setup, the electrolysis could be either acidic or alkaline. While acid electrolysis of water may even find applications in space endeavor, it has associated problems with energy losses (Rossmeisl et al., 2007).

Alkaline electrolysis is a matured technology, with the potential to reduce carbon emission when used in the production of hydrogen. If it is driven by renewable energy. This technology is an uncomplicated way of producing hydrogen, but it is bedeviled by problems of safety concerns, high installation cost and maintenance cost (Rashid et al., 2015). About 4% of the hydrogen produced in the world is currently achieved through

alkaline water electrolysis, when hydrogen is produced using renewable energies such as wind and solar, it is termed as green hydrogen as there is virtually no release of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. However, the main problem facing this manner of production of hydrogen, is the monetary cost incurred. Systems used in this effort require huge capital investment. Presently the production cost of hydrogen using electrolysis is 3 times that when fossil fuels are the energy sources for the hydrogen production (Yang et al., 2022)

While the technology for obtaining hydrogen could be very influential in determining the output, the raw material (in water to be decomposed) may also have an influence on the operation of the electrochemical system and thus the output as well-sea water could be used especially in places where the freshwater usage would be detrimental to livelihood. However, this does not occur without its associated problems. Chlorine evolution reaction could compete with oxygen evolution reaction. Also the high concentration of chlorine could also corrode the anode of electrolyzers and other parts of the electrochemical setup. (Ma et al., 2021).

The aim of the project will be to seek an understanding of the electrochemical kinetics reactions at the electrodes (in relation to various parameters that can influence it) at the electrodes of the electrolytic cell used to produce hydrogen using consumable Anodes. (Zeng and Zhang, 2010) suggest that in order to achieve a good understanding of the of electrode kinetics, one should establish the relationship between the current density and the surface overpotential and the composition of the electrolytic solution adjacent to the electrode surface. The aim is to be fulfilled through the following objectives:

1. Assessing the efficacy of a variety of sacrificial anodes, namely Zn, Sn and Al in electrolytic cell to produce hydrogen production using the Hoffman apparatus.
2. Investigating the role played by the ionic conductivity of the electrolytes-this could be achieved by varying the concentration and PH of the sea water. Further

2 Literature review

2.1 Growing interest in Hydrogen

Ever since the industrial revolution, high economic growth has induced high demand for energy, especially fossil fuels. With this increase in the energy consumption of the world, especially through fossils, the amount of CO_2 in the world has increased as results and the natural carbon cycle is not able to cope. Beside the bad environmental impact posed by the over reliance on the fossils, it is a finite in quantity and potential shortage in the future is possible. (Biodiesel production from waste cooking oil using biochar derived from chicken manure as a porous media and catalyst).

According to (Islam et al., 2016), urbanization is compounding the problem. Fossil fuel usage accounts for 90% of the total CO_2 emissions. Energy demands in transportation, housing and even agriculture release huge amount of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. This carbon dioxide captures heat and thereby increases the average temperatures of the atmosphere. This trend is expected to culminate into a temperature rise of about 1.1 to 6.4 degree Celsius by the turn of the 21st century. However, (Trattner et al., 2022) suggests that renewable energy resources in the sun, wind and hydro developed constantly and comprehensively could ensure not only the constant supply of energy but also enhance the quality of life as zero emission are produced.

That said, with concerns of intermittency in the supply of these energy sources, hydrogen is seen as viable energy store and energy that could even be employed in off-grid areas. Besides, both academia and industry have shown interest in the hydrogen economy-particularly fuelled by the decreasing cost of producing photovoltaic solar system (Abdin et al., 2020).

Even though hydrogen is not readily available in nature, it can be produced using primary sources of energy such as solar and wind. It can be used as fuel for internal combustion engines and it carbon free.it produces water after combustion-producing zero. (Stojić et al., 2003b) supports that hydrogen could be both directly used as fuel for heating systems and electricity production in decentralized fuel cells. It is an efficient means and storage for energy production and transportation, respectively.

Techniques for hydrogen production

According to (Holladay et al., 2009), hydrogen production method may be classified as into the broad category of

- Reforming reaction-hydrocarbon reforming (steam methane reforming, autothermal reforming, partial oxidation), ammonia cracking etc
- Non-reformation reaction

Reforming technique is the processing of a fuel source to produce hydrogen rich product. A typical case in point is the steam methane reforming process which involves methane as a raw material. The process accounts for the greatest part of hydrogen produced in the world today. But also, there are less developed techniques as well-such as ammonia cracking.

Non reforming process for hydrogen production encompasses hydrogen from biomass and hydrogen from water. (Wang et al., 2019a)suggests that biomass can be transformed to syngas, from which hydrogen can be produced. The technologies for the conversion of biomass to energy include combination of gasification, pyrolysis, hydrolysis etc and later biological hydrogen production step. Water splitting technologies also includes thermochemical, photo electrolysis and Electrolysis. Thermochemical and photolysis employs heat and light directly to decompose water into oxygen and hydrogen. Yet Electrolysis employs electricity (which may be derived from various primary sources) to decompose water into hydrogen and oxygen(Holladay et al., 2009).

Electrolysis of water has been a point of attraction for scientist and researchers because of its simplicity, ease of maintenance and the clean fuel it produces. In fact hydrogen is said to be able to produce hydrogen of purity level of about 99.9% vol (ezzahra Chakik et al., 2017).

2.2 Electrolysis of water

Electrolysis of water, typically, enables the decomposition of water into hydrogen and oxygen when direct current is passed through the water. Generally, such an electrolysis system(electrolyser) consists of electrodes, electrolyte and separator (ezzahra Chakik et

al., 2017, Ursua et al., 2011). With an optimum voltage applied across the electrodes, the hydrogen is produced at the cathode while oxygen is produced at the anode (Ezzahra Chakik et al., 2017). The separator or diaphragm is required to allow for the separation of products at the electrode. However, this diaphragm should be able to allow for the passage of ions. Also, this part of the electrochemical setup should be stable, both physically and chemically as the reaction proceeds (Ursua et al., 2011). This reaction of the electrolysis is seen in equation 1

Equation 1

2.2.1 Thermodynamics

As water electrolysis enables the transformation of electrical energy into chemical energy, the process can be described thermodynamically (Ursua et al., 2011). Although the electrolysis reaction requires a theoretical voltage of about 1.23V at 25 degree Celsius and 1atm (Wang et al., 2014, Wang et al., 2021), the real voltage for the reaction is 1.48V- due to the need to overcome resistance in the kinetic, electrolyte and other component of the electrolyser (Kumar and Lim, 2022). Yet, (Chen et al., 2022) suggest that voltages of 2.1V may be required instead of the 1.23V due to electrolysis reaction resistances, even in pure water electrolysis. According to (Yu et al., 2022), there is the need not only to overcome overpotential of the hydrogen evolution reaction and oxygen evolution reaction but also the resistance of the electrolyte diaphragm, contacts and parasitic side reaction. Thus, the overall potential applied may be the sum of the true potential and the losses as results of running the electrolytic system.

(Zeng and Zhang, 2010) suggests that electrolysis of water is a non-spontaneous process and thus require energy for it to proceed. The minimum potential required for the reaction to proceed is Gibbs free energy (ΔG). Gibbs free energy is related to the electrochemical equilibrium voltage (E^o) by the relation

Equation 2

$$\Delta G = nFE^o$$

According to (Ursua et al., 2011), at constant temperature and pressure, Gibbs free energy is equal in value to the value of enthalpy of the process minus the magnitude of

thermal energy (multiple of the temperature(T) and entropy(ΔS)) required for the electrolysis to take place.

Equation 3

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$$

Since electrolysis cannot occur spontaneously, the voltage in the process is said to be the reverse cell voltage (V_r). this is the minimum voltage required for the electrolysis of water to occur. This energy is also known as thermoneutral energy required for electrolysis to occur. This can be represented mathematically as

Equation 4

$$V_r = \frac{\Delta G}{zF}$$

For hydrogen $z=2$ and F is the faradays constant (96485Cmol^{-1}) there is an ideal voltage (V_r), but the actual voltage V_a is normally greater as there is additional energy consumption in the cell-energy to produce a thermal effect for the electrolysis occur.

2.2.2 Efficiency of Electrolysis

According to (Wang et al., 2014), current could be fully converted into the splitting water based on the faradays law, which says for every 1 mol of hydrogen, 2 times the faradays constant of charge is required. Besides, To ensure the efficient production of hydrogen in the electrolysis of water, the right electrodes have to be engineered-such electrodes should offer lower overpotentials and stability(Zhou et al., 2020).Thus Electrode material amongst other properties may be key in determining the efficiency of electrolysis of water.

2.2.2.1 Factors affecting the efficiency of Electrolysis of water

2.2.2.1.1 Overpotential

While water electrolysis by itself requires a thermodynamic voltage of 1.23v to over ensure a reaction occurs, there is yet also a barrier in overpotential, as results of kinetic barriers, to overcome in order to guarantee the occurrence of water electrolysis. According to(David et al., 2019),overpotential may be attributable to the polarization of the electrode(formation of the double layer effect) and the conductivity of material in the path of current flow in between the electrodes-essentially overpotential depends on the ionic and the electrical conductivity of the electrolyte.

2.2.2.1.2 Electrolyte Quality

(Mazloomi and Sulaiman, 2012) says that the electrolyte as part of the electrochemical setup for water electrolysis ensures the flow of current through the system. Bases and acids are dissolved in water to bring about the conductivity of current. Yet these chemicals could have negative impact on the stability of the parts of the electrolytic cell, such as membrane and electrodes. The corrosive nature of acid and bases could shorten the lifetime of the electrochemical setup if limits are not in place. (Colli et al., 2019) suggest that for example existing alkaline water electrolysis technology uses NaOH or KOH aqueous solution of the range(20-40%).Yet KOH is normally preferred as its corrosive effect is lower compared to NaOH(Zeng and Zhang, 2010).In (De Souza et al., 2007),whiles various electrodes(electrocatalyst) in nickel,304 stainless steel and low carbon steel,BMI.BF₄ ionic aqueous solution of 10% volume, as electrolyte, was used to achieve hydrogen production efficiency of 95%-99%.

Also the presence of impurities such as Mg, Cl or calcium ions could also be a cause for concern as they tend to not only reduce the effective surface area of electrodes but also promote side reactions (Mazloomi and Sulaiman, 2012).

2.2.2.1.3 Electrode material

According to (Fiegenbaum et al., 2015, Colli et al., 2019, Hauch et al., 2008), material used in electrodes varies widely but is restricted in alkaline electrolysis because of the corrosive nature of the electrolyte. The important properties of electrodes are surface area, catalytic activities, electrical resistance, corrosion resistivity and durability. Platinum and Palladium are renowned for their high performance (show low polarization especially for oxygen evolution), yet they have a high price tag. Thus, cheaper options such as Fe, cobalt, nickel and other alloys are used in industries. Further, (De Souza et al., 2008) suggest that even though platinum electrodes' reaction kinetics in KOH electrolyte is relatively impressive, it lags behind the performance of Molybdenum in BMI.BF₄ ionic electrolyte. As electrode materials vary widely, there should be a way of comparing their performance.

The main way of comparison for these electrodes (cathodes and anodes) is through the polarization curve as in Figure 1. Polarization curves for several electrode materials (catalysts) at 30 degrees Celsius.

Figure 1. polarization curves for several electrode material(catalyst) at 30 degrees Celsius

however according to (Colli et al., 2019),this could be problematic as polarization curve may differ depending on the author that produces it.

2.2.2.1.4 Temperature

(Hauch et al., 2008) suggest that electrolysis which is an endothermic reaction can be presented according to the Equation 5

Equation 5

Thermodynamically, when electrolysis run at high temperature and if the heat requirement could be delivered by high temperature, then the energy requirement to ensure that electrolysis occur is reduced. Also at high temperature, kinetics of the reactions that culminate into electrolysis are enhanced thus reducing the energy losses through ohmic resistance and polarization losses at the electrodes.

Moreover,(Stojić et al., 2003a) says that for temperature range between 253K to 353K,the energy requirement for producing a specific amount of H_2 reduces with increasing temperature .For an applied voltage, high temperatures promote high current densities at the cathode.

2.2.2.1.5 Gap between the electrodes

According to (Mazloomi and Sulaiman, 2012), reducing the space between the electrode yield a lower electrical resistance but the extent of space reduction matters. If the electrodes are too close, it can be counterproductive leading to reduced efficiency.

(Nagai et al., 2003) mentions that since voltage required for the electrolysis process encompasses reverse potential for electrolysis, overpotential of electrodes and ohmic losses should be at play but an overemphasis on only ensuring other requirement, apart from the latter, are met will not enhance efficiency. Ohmic losses are attributable to the distance between the electrodes. Also, the combination of the extent of current density and distances could be influential. There is an optimum distance between electrodes (couple with appropriate current density but if the current density is too high and the gap between electrodes are too small, the tendency for the formation of void fraction (due to formation of bubbles) between the electrodes increases-this increase results in the increase in electrical resistance and subsequently a decrease in the efficiency of the electrolysis of water.(Swiegers et al., 2021) says that Bruggeman Equation 6 and Figure 2 can below could be used to show a simple relation between the conductivity of the electrolyte and the void fraction in between the electrodes.

Equation 6

$$K = K_0(1 - \epsilon)^{\frac{3}{2}}$$

Figure 2- Swiegers et al., 2021

2.3 Classification of water Electrolysis

2.3.1 Conventional electrolysis versus emerging (non-conventional) electrolysis

The configuration of a conventional setup for the electrolysis of water, which may also be known as a coupled setup, has a diaphragm to separate the main products of oxygen and hydrogen in a single cell. This could engender mixing of the products—a situation which can have safety concerns. However, a decoupled setup which is a variation of the typical configuration ensures this does not happen. For a decoupled electrolytic setup for water splitting, the evolution reaction at the anode produces oxygen and a cathodic product of hydrogen are produced in different cells thus the tendency to mix for the formation of combustion mixture is prevented. While these changes may come with additional cost as different cell setups are required for the collection of different products, it can be a solution to the main cause of the hazard posed, the intermittency of power supply and low current densities in the operation of the electrochemical system for water electrolysis (Symes and Cronin, 2013).

Further in conventional electrolysis, despite various developments in electrocatalysts and improvements in technologies, the required voltage to achieve 10mA/cm^2 in an electrolytic water system is still greater than 1.4 volts—the oxygen evolution reaction is seen as requiring high energy due to slow reaction at the anode (Wang et al., 2019b).

2.3.2 Classification according to main Electrolyser

(Kumar and Lim, 2022) says based on the type of electrolyte, ionic agents and operating condition, various water splitting technologies have been defined. They are mainly

- Alkaline water electrolysis (AWE)
- Solid oxide Electrolysis (SOE)
- Microbial electrolysis cell (MEC)
- PEM water electrolysis

2.3.2.1 Types of electrolysers

(Mohammadi and Mehrpooya, 2018) says electrolyser could be termed as the opposite of fuel cells—in fuel cells electrical energy and water is produced from the reaction of the

hydrogen and oxygen while in an electrolyser electrical energy is used to breakdown water into oxygen and hydrogen.

The main types of electrolyzers used for water splitting are Alkaline, proton exchange membrane (PEM) and solid oxide electrolyser (SOE)

2.3.2.1.1 PEM

(Pham et al., 2021) says that PEM electrolyzers consist of proton exchange membrane enclosed in two bipolar plates (anode and the cathode). The bipolar plates which form the outer casing of the cell is connected to a water supply as well as storage in which products can be stored. In between the anode and the membrane is a porous of packing of tin while in between the cathode and the membrane, there is also porous packing of say carbon. A catalyst that hastens the kinetics of the reaction is found on either side of the of the permeable membrane, as layer, on the anode side (oxygen evolution) and the cathode (hydrogen evolution) purposes.

Figure 3-diagram of pem operating principle-(Ursua et al., 2011)

(Ursua et al., 2011) suggest that hydrogen electrodes of a PEM cell are normally made of noble metals (metals that do not corrode)-example of which are platinum and Iridium. During the running of this type of electrolyser, anodic reaction results in the oxidation

of water to form proton that travels through the permeable membrane to be reduced at the cathode

anode

Equation 7

Cathode

Equation 8

The product in hydrogen produced in PEM cell is about 99.99%vol. Also, PEM electrolyser s can achieve high current densities relative to alkaline electrolyzers.

The drawback of PEM electrolyser is the high initial cost of investment due to the membrane and the noble-metal electrodes. Also its stability is questionable over the long term(Ursua et al., 2011).Further this type of electrolyser can only split water of high purity -conductivity of water should be about 1μS/cm.

2.3.2.1.2 Solid oxide electrolyser

Even though it is the least utilized among the electrolyser, this water electrolyser has high efficiency. It runs at high temperatures and requires less electricity for its operation. However the material used for the production of such electrolyser requirement high temperature-resistant properties to withstand the operation temperature(Stempien et al., 2013).In (Frey et al., 2018) suggest that to make the introduction of such an electrolyser on the market possible, rapid degradation of such an equipment should be dealt-prolonging the life span.

In the electrolysis process steam and recycled hydrogen fed through the cathode enable the reduction the steam by obeying the Equation 9.The oxide ion generated passes through a solid electrolyte to the anode where they release electrons to form oxygen according to the Equation 10

Equation 9

2.3.2.1.3 Alkaline electrolyser

This is the most widely used water electrolyser in the industry and it is highly proven. It possesses high efficiency of up to about 82%. It is relatively affordable technology compared to the others (Kotowicz et al., 2016, Mohammadi and Mehrpooya, 2018). Alkaline water electrolyzers also may not necessarily require noble metals as electrodes, metals which can be expensive, thereby ensuring cost reduction (Colli et al., 2019). Besides, the hydrogen produced by an alkaline electrolyser is of high purity - in the range of 99.7% to 99.9%. This type of electrolyser can split relatively less pure water (like seawater) - with conductivity of $5\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (Kotowicz et al., 2016).

Figure 4-diagram of the alkaline electrolyser-(Ursua et al., 2011)

The electrolyser consists of two electrodes in touch with an electrolyte (the water to be split and normally some amount of KOH or NaOH). The cathodes are separated by a polymeric membrane to prevent the mixing of the products from electrolysis. (Mohammadi and Mehrpooya, 2018) suggests the amount of KOH or NaOH and water

mixture, making up the electrolyte, is about 30wt% of either KOH or NaOH. In this electrolyser, as opposed to the PEM electrolyser, the water is fed through the cathode and the following reactions Equation 11 and Equation 12 ensue:

Anode

Equation 11

Cathode

Equation 12

2.4 Hybrid electrolysis

According to (Chen et al., 2022), hybrid electrolysis is splitting of water molecules with an alternative oxidation reaction (rather than oxygen evolution reaction) occurring at the anode while hydrogen evolution is maintained at the cathode. This alternate route to oxidation reaction ensures a reduction in the energy input for the electrolysis to be done.

For example (Sun et al., 2021) suggest that reaction at the anode of an electrolytic cell for the production of hydrogen could be changed-replaced by a more energy saving and environmentally friendly alternative. In the said research, oxidation of chlorine which could potentially compete with oxygen evolution reaction at the cathode was replaced by employing hydrazine in an electrolytic cell to produce hydrogen. During their electrolysis of seawater, as H_2O is broken down at the cathode to form H_2 and OH^- , the latter would pass through a diaphragm to combine with hydrazine (N_2H_4) to form N_2 and H_2O .

Figure 5-hybrid electrolysis and benefits

Figure 6-Typical electrolysis

2.5 Seawater electrolysis

The attraction to seawater electrolysis may be in part due to its abundance, the main raw material on earth, as fresh water is limited to mostly human consumption and encroaching this supply for anthropogenic activities could be problematic (Liu et al., 2022). Thus, the sea remains a very good source of water for electrolysis, but this comes with its own challenges.

Challenges and opportunities for sea water Electrolysis

(Liu et al., 2022) suggest that chlorine reaction in seawater occurs at a voltage of 1.7V in alkaline solution thus there is the need to have an anode that ensures that oxidation reactions occur at a lower potential than the said voltage. Also, seawater may contain impurities which are insoluble impurities, which can compromise electrodes and affect the long-term stability of the electrochemical system. The need for anode material that will not only ensure stability but also ensure efficient oxidation is therefore an important requirement. Moreover, the overpotential as a result of these impurities such as Na⁺, Cl⁻, Ca, K⁺, OH⁻ etc and possible adverse reaction at the cathode, the overpotential for seawater electrolysis is higher than that of fresh water. An overpotential of 319mV, 332mV and 346mV were reported for electrolytic cells at current density for 10mAcm⁻² with electrolytes in 1M KOH freshwater solution, alkaline simulated

seawater (with 1M KOH+0.5M NaCl) and alkaline natural seawater (1M KOH) respectively.

According to (Gao et al., 2022, Fukuzumi et al., 2017), even though the conversion of Chloride ions to Chlorine or the conversion of Cl₂ to hypochlorite in alkaline solution are both two electron two electron process and kinetically more favourable, achieving them require an overpotential of about 480mV compared to oxygen evolution reaction (or even more overpotential in a modified oxidation reaction in the water-electrolytic system). In alkaline medium, Chloride ions will tend to convert to hypochlorite and therein lies the advantage -with a barrier to reach in over potential of 480mV to achieve chlorine gas at the anode. Essentially in alkaline medium if a suitable electrode (with appropriate electrocatalyst) could be obtained, chlorine evolution reactions will always be suppressed in favour of oxygen evolution reaction or even better alternate oxidation reaction at the anode.

Solution to Challenges of Seawater Electrolysis

(Zheng et al., 2021) suggest that the two main ways of overcoming the challenges in seawater electrolysis that have been pursued by researcher are the used of electrode engineering and catalyst optimization strategies. The former focuses on issues such as electrode surface blockages and physical damage during operation. On the other hand, the latter focuses on decreasing unwanted reaction such chloride oxidation, electrocatalyst corrosion and the poisoning of electrocatalyst.

The catalyst design strategy may encompass the selection of the catalyst that enhances the either electrode reaction or one that is corrosion resistance. The selection of these electrodes could particularly be helped by tuning the PH of the electrolytes appropriately to aid the efficiency of the selected electrodes.

According to (Fan et al., 2022), to deal with the challenges of seawater, specifically the direct seawater electrolysis, the development of high efficiency non-noble metal based anodic oxygen evolution material with chlorine corrosion resistant properties should be the main focus for researcher. Fan and his colleagues were able to develop an anode, which with anodic corrosion, could renew itself in the upon exposure to Chlorine corrosion in seawater. The anode was constructed by using a catalyst of Fe-

Ni(oxy)hydroxide on the surface of Fe-Ni electrode. Besides its particularly surprising nature, the said anodic material could produce a current density of 100mAcm^{-1} with an overpotential of 252mV to deal with. Also(Yu et al., 2019) ,with a three dimensional metal nitride catalyst uniformly spread on NiMoN nanorods as anode and was able to achieve active and enduring oxygen evolution reaction during an alkaline seawater electrolysis. Yu and colleague were able to achieve current densities of 500 and 1000mAcm^{-1} with applied voltages of 1.608 and 1.709V respectively at 60 degree Celsius.

(Zheng et al., 2021) also mentions the mention that in electrode in engineering efforts, surface protection may be offered to electrodes to act as passivation layer on top other active.it is made known that carbon shell coating used in protecting electrode material could prevent dissolution of electrocatalyst in electrolytes. Also, mention is made of CeOx coating-renowned for protecting catalyst and ensuring their stability over 90hr of electrolysis process. Besides this, Zheng and colleagues also talk about need to ensure that electrodes/electrocatalyst do not only promote the formation bubble but also to be able to release produced bubbles appropriately -a situation that could reduce losses due to ohmic drop and drop in mass transfer.

Electrochemical measurement principles

Electrode reaction theory

(Bamford et al., 1986) suggest total charge(Q) for electrons consumed or produced at an electrode can be given by the equation

Equation 13

$$Q = nFN$$

Where F is the faradays constant, equal to 96485C/mol, n is the number electron while N is the number of moles of product produced or reactant consumed. Thus, the passage of a charge of 96485.3 will cause the production of 1 mol product or the consumption of one mole reactant. The charge(Q) per unit time is the current and therefore the current passed at an electrode determines the rate (kinetics) of the reaction at the electrode-the relationship is directly proportional. But since the reaction at the electrode is a heterogenous one and reaction is assumed to occur at the surface of

electrode/electrolyte interface, the current per unit area (current) and product or reactant consumption per unit area are considered. Thus, the relation may be written as in Equation 14

and the rate as in Equation 15

Equation 14

$$\frac{i}{A} = \frac{dQ}{dtA} = nF \frac{dN}{dtA}$$

Equation 15

$$rate\left(\frac{mol}{scm^2}\right) = i/nFA$$

As a result, the rate of production of hydrogen at the cathode could be calculated in an electrolysis experimental setup once the current density is determined after the application of a voltage across the electrodes.

Electrochemical impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

Traditional electrochemical measurements have limit in the extent of information that it can provide about the electrode-electrolyte interface. To give a more complete view about an electrochemical system, EIS technique is a handy tool. This technique makes it possible to separate the faradaic and non-faradaic elements in a circuit. An electrochemical system can be imagined as one with a resistor, capacitor and in some other inductor (Park and Yoo, 2003).

Although initially applied to the determination of double layer capacitance and in ac polarography, recently EIS has seen widespread usage especially as now employed in the characterization of electrode reaction and even complex interfaces. This process enables the measurement of a systems response to periodic small-amplitude ac signal. The output of this procedure can give insights about interface, structure as well as the reaction of the subject. Whiles these may obviously be important information, it only complements other electrochemical techniques in know more about an electrolytic system (Lasia, 2002).

Principles of EIS

According to (Barsukov and Macdonald, 2012), While current flow through typical resistors could be explained by ohms law, where in various voltages applied to yield various currents may yield constant resistance, electrochemical systems may not exactly exhibit this phenomenon as there may be other components such capacitors. This is because resistor may tend to dissipate energy, but capacitors tend to store energy. Also, current and voltage value are time dependant.

However, there is a way of treating such systems and their current voltage be behaviour with respect to component such as capacitors and/or inductors. Through the Laplace transform, the current voltage may be written in an ohm-like format but with consideration for the time dependence for the voltage and current as follows

Equation 16

$$I(s) = \frac{V(s)}{Z(s)}$$

Equation 17

$$s = Re + i\omega$$

Where $I(s)$, $V(s)$ and $Z(s)$ are complex current, complex voltage and complex resistance (also known an impedance) and ω is the frequency which depends on time. Even in the eighteen century this principle of EIS was applicable when a voltage of sinusoidal wave form of the in Equation 18 will be applied and after a period of stabilisation produce a current of equivalent wave form but of difference phase value

Equation 18

$$V(t) = V \sin \omega t$$

The is produces a current output out of phase with the voltage and because even back then there was analogue equipment that could measure both the magnitude and phase change in voltage or current, impedance could be determined.

However, presently, computers may be used to produce EIS data that can mainly be presented in a spectrum. The models produced can approximate values of impedance from discrete circuit-like element and thus simplify the complex nature of electrochemical setups. In fact the Butler-Volmer equation, suggest that at very low excitation voltage, there is a linear relationship between current and voltage. Thus, for an electrochemical system, the complex nature electrochemical setup at a small excitation voltage can be done with simple electrical elements- thus it can be described by relation like the ohms law.

Measurements for the producing the spectrum may be achieved by modulating the voltage or current signal. The devices (connected to a computer which gives produces) for modulating the current and voltages are Galvanostat and potentiostat respectively. The impedance spectrum is the main output in this measurement. The bode and Nyquist plot are the main forms of this spectrum.

3 Methodology

The method used mainly in this experiment was the quantitative method, which was to produce data as a way of the describing the characteristics that fulfil my objectives-quantifying (through various indicators) the potency of various metals to produce hydrogen gas. Further to that I was to determine the extent of influence the concentration of electrolyte used in the Hoffman apparatus had on the hydrogen production rate.

Equipment

Hoffman Apparatus, Voltage source, Voltmeter, Ammeter, PH meter and the Gamry.

Figure 7- A hoffman apparatus

Figure 8-A block diagram showing equipment using in Hoffman experiments

3.1 Procedure

Various molar concentration(1M,2M,4M) of aqueous solution were prepared at room temperature and pressure. Electrolytic cells were constructed with various anodes - namely Zn, Sn, Al etc. as anodes and in all case stainless steel was used as the cathode with the temperature at the which the experiment was done was noted as about 21 degrees Celsius.

With different voltages from 1-2V applied across the electrodes of the electrolyser (Hoffman Apparatus), measure the current, amount of current that flows in the setup, the amount of H_2 produced and the time required for such production was noted.

Also, an electrochemical impedance spectroscopy on the electrolytic setup to determine the resistance in the in the electrolytic system -mainly the resistance in the solution and the resistance to charge transfer.

3.2 Preparation of standard solution of NaCl

Standard solution of NaCl were prepared as a way of mimicking seawater. The mass for the preparation of the aqueous solution of NaCl was first determined by molar calculation method to derive the mass to NaCl to be weighed. The amount of NaCl was then weighed using the sensitive balance (making sure that window of the weigh-in area is closed), and that balance accommodated any unevenness on the working countertop. The amount of NaCl was then put in a Volumetric Flask and topped to the required volume whiles stirring to achieve a uniform solution.

3.3 Installation of electrodes and filling of electrolyte in the Hoffman cell

The Hoffman apparatus(electrolyser) has two opened at the bottom to receive the metal(electrodes). The electrodes (metal plates) were stuck in a pin-like titanium metal and the titanium metal also fit into a bubble bung. These bubble bungs were

then stuck into the opening at the base of the Hoffman voltameter for the both the cathode and the anode-with the connections of terminals from the voltage sources determining the anode and the cathode-positive terminal to anode and negative terminal to the cathode. The metal electrodes were firmly fit to titanium pin and exposed to the electrolyte when filled whiles the bubble bung fitting at the bases of the Hoffman apparatus was checked for leaks as the water with various molar concentrations of salt was introduced from the top of the Hoffman apparatus.

In filling the Hoffman apparatus, spout-taps at the top were opened initially to allow for the evacuation of any air in the setup as the electrolyte is first introduced. After the Hoffman apparatus is filled to the desired level-point where there is enough cavity at the top of the middle arm of the apparatus to allow for electrolyte displacement, the spout on either side of the middle arm the Hoffman apparatus was closed.

3.4 Operation of the Hoffman during the experiment

A voltage source is applied across the electrodes after the electrodes to the Hoffman are fitted. The positive terminal of the voltage source was fitted to the anode while the negative terminal of the voltage source was fitted to the cathode.

With the spouts in the arms of the Hoffman closed, the voltage source turned on causes the flow of current and the subsequently the production of gas(es) at the electrodes - hydrogen at the cathode and/or oxygen at the anode. This gas produced displaces the water in the arm of the Hoffman depending on the electrode that is at the base of the arm of the Hoffman. For as was mostly the case in my setup the anode was at the base of the left arm of the Hoffman, thus any gas(oxygen) that was released was released into the left arm while the cathode gas produced was released into the right arm since the cathode was at the base of the right arm of the Hoffman apparatus.

3.5 Test of the gases

A pop test was used to test for the presence of hydrogen gas. This was done by employing a lighter and a narrow test tube used to collect the gas as the spout was opened after experiments.

Also, to test for any oxygen, it was to be tested by using a narrow test tube to collect the oxygen and check if it will relight a burning splint.

3.6 Data Collected and Visualization of data

Data from the experiment collected was fed into an excel sheet and the plots of the gas evolved in each experiment set was plotted against the time period in which it was produced. The slope of the linear plot was to be used as the gas evolution rate and thus a measure of the kinetics of the reaction with a particular metal as the anodes are to be checked.

Based on the volumetric evolution of gas values, the data can be converted to molar rate of evolution by dividing the former by 24 (using Charles law and molar volume).

4 Results

As a way of measuring the kinetics of the reaction at particularly the anode various metal (Zn, Sn and Al) material were used as anode material while the cathode material in the electrolysis setup was maintained as the stainless steel. In doing this, various voltages were applied across the electrodes to ascertain the characteristics of current density, hydrogen production rate, secondary reactions (alternate reaction to oxygen evolution reaction at anode) and the efficiency of current conversion to hydrogen production.

The metals used as anode material were Zinc, Tin and aluminium. The following results were obtained for each anode's electrolytic system-using the Hoffman apparatus.

Zinc anode

With Zn as the anode, with a surface area of 12.5cm^2 , in the electrolysis setup, voltages of 1V, 1.2V, 1.4V, 1.6V, 1.8V and 2.0V were applied across the electrodes for different molar concentrations (1M, 2M, 4M) of aqueous NaCl solution used as electrolyte in Hoffman apparatus. The application of these voltages cause variation in current density, secondary reaction at the anode, hydrogen production rate.

The values of current density rose as the voltage applied increased for various molar concentrations of aqueous NaCl used as electrolyte. The least current density registered was for a 1M NaCl solution and it was $0.385\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ (at 1V) at room laboratory temperature (about 21 degrees Celsius) while the highest for the same setup was $0.885\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ (at 2V). For the 2M NaCl electrolysis system the lowest current density, which was $0.64\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ at 1V rose through incrementally voltages till the value of the current density peaked to $1.50\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ at 2V. The same trend was seen in the setup with a 4M electrolyte with lowest value of current density of $0.99\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ at 1V and $2.4\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ at 2V. Figure 9 shows the impact of increasing molar concentration of electrolyte on current density values.

Figure 9-Polarization curves for different concentration of electrolytes

After the modification of the PH of the 4M electrolyte of the electrolytic system to a ph. of 12, current densities for voltages of 0.6V,1.2 and 1.6 were 0.44mA/cm²,1.2mA/cm² and 1.76mA/cm² respectively. the table

In terms of secondary reaction, the Zn anode in the electrolytic setup developed white chalky like formation develops on the zinc anode and its very visible after the electrolysis is complete. There was no visible gas evolution at the anode arm of the Hoffman apparatus but there was evolution of the hydrogen gas at the cathode.

Gas production as a measure of the kinetics of the reaction at the anode and the cathode measured with two main variable-they were the voltage and molar concentration of the aqueous NaCl solution (artificial seawater used). Figure 11,Figure 12 and Figure 13 show how voltage increase affects the evolution rate of hydrogen at the cathode for 4M,2M and 1M electrolyte used respectively. The PH variation was done for only 4M aqueous

electrolytic setup. The Figure 10 shows the effect of this variation on the current density values.

Figure 10-comparing the polarization in all electrolytes-setups (including 4M with PH of 12)

Figure 11-hydrogen evolution data for different voltages for 4M electrolyte

Figure 12-hydrogen evolution data for 2M electrolyte

Figure 13-hydrogen evolution data for 1M electrolyte

voltage(v)	current density(mA/cm²)	rate (mol/s)	Rate/A (mol/scm²)	Faradaic efficiency
2	0.8848	4.82529E-08	3.84E-09	84.18955147
1.8	0.7992	4.7005E-08	3.7E-09	90.79632877
1.6	0.6504	3.52745E-08	2.81E-09	83.72605723
1.4	0.5656	3.22379E-08	2.58E-09	87.99087212
1.2	0.4832	2.73295E-08	2.16E-09	87.31397588
1	0.3848	2.16306E-08	1.73E-09	86.7787921

Table 1-current density, rate of hydrogen evolution and faradic efficiency for electrolysis with 1M NaCl

voltage	current density(mA/cm²)	rate (mol/s)	expected rate/area mol/scm²	Faradaic efficiency (%)
2	1.4992	9.25917E-08	7.40E-09	95.34372421
1.8	1.3504	8.12167E-08	6.49E-09	92.84585407
1.6	1.1552	6.11625E-08	4.88E-09	81.73495585
1.4	0.984	5.55542E-08	4.44E-09	87.15680928
1.2	0.8152	4.86125E-08	3.82E-09	92.05843106
1	0.6392	3.80429E-08	3.04E-09	91.87911926

Table 2-current density, rate of hydrogen evolution and faradic efficiency for electrolysis with 2M

voltage	current density(A/cm ²)	rate (mol/s)	expected	Faradaic efficiency (%)
			rate/Area (mol/scm ²)	
2	2.4	1.40278E-07	1.12E-08	90.23134259
1.8	2.1464	1.425E-07	1.14E-08	102.4905889
1.6	1.864	1.26042E-07	1.00E-08	104.3873838
1.4	1.5752	1.10417E-07	8.80E-09	108.2128195
1.2	1.3232	8.36111E-08	6.67E-09	97.54798132
1	0.9864	6.4375E-08	5.12E-09	100.7497466

Table 3- current density, rate of hydrogen evolution and faradic efficiency for electrolysis with 4M

voltage	current density(A/cm ²)	rate (mol/s)	expected	Faradaic efficiency (%)
			rate(mol/s)	
1.6	1.7568	1.22222E-07	9.76E-09	107.4008298
1.2	1.2128	7.11111E-08	5.60E-09	90.51656406
0.6	0.4416	2.68056E-08	2.140E-09	93.70775463

Table 4- current density, rate of hydrogen evolution and faradic efficiency of Zn for electrolysis with 4M with PH 12

Tin anode

With tin, with a surface area of 12.5cm², as the anode for the electrolytic setup, hydrogen production, current density and secondary reaction were obtained from the electrolysis experimental procedure. However, the experiment with the Hoffman apparatus was run with only 4M electrolyte.

In this anode-electrolytic cell, only the hydrogen evolution reaction at the cathode was observed but there was visible white precipitate formation around the cathode. The current densities and hydrogen production rate rose as voltages increased.

voltage	current density(mA/cm ²)	rate (mol/s)	Rate/area (mol/scm ²)	Faradaic efficiency (%)
2	1.6112	9.52083E-08	7.6E-09	91.22319803
1.8	1.3232	8.04167E-08	6.4E-09	93.82106509
1.6	1.0904	6.34583E-08	5.04E-09	89.84266019
1.2	0.4896	3.39E-08	2.71E-09	106.8902451

Table 5- current density, rate of hydrogen evolution and faradic efficiency of Sn for electrolysis with 4M

At 1.2V voltage the production of rate of hydrogen was 3.39E-08 mol/s. This production rate increased for each voltage increment until a maximum value of 9.52083E-08mol/s was reached for the highest voltage applied voltage. The Table 5**Error! Reference source not found.** shows this trend as well as the faradaic efficiency values for the set of experiments.

Figure 14 hydrogen evolution graph-volume against time for Sn anode setup

Al as anode

Working with aluminium as anode, with surface area of 11.67cm^2 , current density, rate production on rate and the reactions at the electrodes were also observed. The voltages chosen for these observations were 1V and 1.6 and 2V

The experiment set produced gas evolution at both the cathode (hydrogen evolution reaction) and at the anode (oxygen evolution reaction). However, there was no visible reaction precipitate formation in the reaction during run of the experiment over the 1-hour period.

The current densities produced in these set of experiments were $2.0\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$, $1.2\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ and $0.571\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$. These currents were transformed into hydrogen production at efficiency values of 94%, 92% and 94% for the current density values given respectively. The hydrogen production rate at 1V was the lowest at about $3.17083\text{E} - 08\text{mols}^{-1}$

while the highest hydrogen production rate was about $1.12083E - 07 \text{mols}^{-1}$ at 2V. This was in line with the trend that hydrogen production rate increases with increasing voltage. But, with this anode-electrolytic cell, oxygen evolution was observed in at the anode. While the production rate also increases with increase in voltage, the gas production rate was relatively low compared to the flow rate of hydrogen produced at the cathode. The minimum gas production rate at the anode recorded in the experiment was about $1.04167E - 08 \text{mols}^{-1}$ while the highest at 2.0V of applied voltage was about $2.79167E - 08 \text{mols}^{-1}$.

Figure 15 hydrogen evolution rate for Al-anode setup

Figure 16 oxygen evolution rate at anode on Al-electrolytic setup

The efficiency faradaic conversion of the current into gas production was very efficient for the hydrogen production with efficiency values above the 90 percent but the same could not be achieved for the oxygen evolution at the cathode. The faradaic efficiency for both hydrogen evolution and oxygen evolution could be found Table 6 and Table 7 below.

voltage	current density(mA/cm ²)	rate (mol/s)	Rate/area(mol/s cm ²)	Faradaic efficiency (%)
2	2.021800281	1.12083E-07	9.89E-09	94.03824036
1.6	1.230661041	6.70833E-08	5.89E-09	92.46510993
1	0.57137834	3.17083E-08	2.96E-09	94.13472436

Table 6- current density, rate of hydrogen evolution and faradic efficiency of Al for electrolysis with 4M

voltage	current density(mA/cm ²)	rate of (mol/s)	expected rate (mol/scm ²)	Faradaic efficiency (%)
2	2.021800281	2.79167E-08	2.25E-09	23.422164
1.6	1.230661041	1.04167E-08	9.15E-10	14.3579363

Table 7-- current density, rate of oxygen evolution and faradic efficiency of Al for electrolysis with 4M

Lastly of all the consumable anode in Zn, Al and Tn used in the artificial seawater experiment of mostly 4M electrolyte solution, Al lost the most weight during the process and both Sn and Tin maintained their weight of just about 2hr electrolysis process.

Metal	Weight before	Weight after
Zn	2.2	2.2
Sn	3.4	3.4
Al	1.22	0.96

Table 8-weight loss for consumable anodes after about 2hr electrolysis in hoffman apparatus

5 Discussion

With the kinetics of the reaction at the electrodes, while it depends on the electrolyte concentration and the voltage applied and even the fittings used to put the electrolysis system together, it also depends considerably on the nature of the material used for the electrodes. This is suggested by (Zhou et al., 2020). The experiments undertaken showed that different anodes may contribute to the current densities achieved in the electrolysis system differently and thus have varied impact on the hydrogen production rate.

Zn anode produced relatively the best current densities for the same voltage and electrolytes concentration used. Zn may be oxidized to at the anode to Zn^{2+} while Al and Sn may be oxidized to Al^{3+} and Sn^{2+} respectively at the anode the electrochemical series the reactivity is lowest for Sn (with -0.36 reduction potential) and highest for aluminium (-1.76) with Zn with medium reactivity. Even though Al is expected to react relatively in the most active manner to give the highest electron flow per unit area of the anode and thus high current density, that is not the case. On the contrary the Zn reacts much better to produce a much high current density. This may be explained by the fact that Al oxidation is a three-electron process and that kinetically not a favourable compared to the Zn electrode and Sn electrode. Also, Aluminium is known to have a more much stable Al_2O_3 coating on its surface and this probably make the release of electron very difficult with the coating. Also (Sun et al., 2021) suggests that hybrid electrolysis reactions (with alternate reaction to oxygen evolution reaction at the anode) could be more efficient than the traditional electrolysis, in which oxygen evolution reaction occurs thus the efficiency of the Al-anode electrolytic setup may have been compromised because it exhibited oxygen evolution reaction relative to Zn-anode setup. Also, quantitatively when the values of current density are collated for the voltages of 2.0V and 1.6V for the same 4M solutions for Zn Sn and Al electrolytic setup, as seen in the Table 9 current density obtained at 2V and 1.6V for various anode with 4M aqueous NaCl, the data shows that Zn can achieve a current density of 1.86mA/cm² even with a voltage of 1.6 volts applied but Sn anode setup requires a voltage of 2V to achieve just a 1.60mA/cm². In fact, the Sn-anode setup would have to overcome an overpotential of at least 400mV in order to achieve the current density that Zn-anode system achieves at

1.6V. This could be observed in Table 9. The current densities are further translated into similar hydrogen production.

Voltage	current density(mA/cm ²)		
	Zn	Sn	Al
2	2.4	1.612	2.02
1.6	1.86	1.09	1.23

Table 9 current density obtained at 2V and 1.6V for various anode with 4M aqueous NaCl

This is particularly so as the faradaic efficiency of the various anode-electrolytic setup hover around the 90% mark generally signalling high conversion of current to output in hydrogen. While some data point may be erroneous due to a due to parallax and rapid bubbling of gases during measurement especially for the setup with 4M electrolyte, resulting in efficiency going over 100%, the general theme is that faradaic efficiency is quite good and high current densities will translate into high hydrogen production rate. Thus, Zn anode, generating the highest current densities obtained high hydrogen production rate with Sn having the least current densities getting the least hydrogen production rates at the same voltage with same concentration of electrolytes used and Al setup with medium hydrogen production rates.

Secondary reaction took place in Zn-anode and the Sn-anode electrolytic setups. According to (Khan et al., 2021), the electrolyte solution becomes more basic (that this increase could be by about 5-9Ph units) especially around the electrodes as the electrolysis process ongoing, there tend to be white precipitate forming around the cathode. This was seen in the Sn-anode electrolysis setup but in the Zn electrode the precipitation was seen around the anode. While this experiment was undertaken in a relatively short period of time, and the effect of such occurrence may not have been particularly evident even with Zn anode's partial obscurity. This anode produced the highest current density and engendered the highest hydrogen production rate. But the case could be different if an electrolyser with a long period of operation uses such an anode. This could have negative implication on the formation of hydrogen at cathode

directly especially if the surface of the anode and subsequently hamper the reaction of Zn anode and the electrolyte. In the long term such anodes will have to be changed when required. A remedy for this may be to regulate the PH of the electrolyte, an action The molar concentration of artificial seawater (aqueous NaCl) in the Hoffman apparatus influences the output of gas production positively-as the concentration of the electrolyte increase the current densities achieved for the electrolytic setup increased. For example, the maximum hydrogen production rate when 1 M However, this increase in Molarity of electrolyte come with the potential for the electrolyte to cause the formation of precipitates on around the electrodes. Precipitates that can occupy effective surface are on which gas are produced leading reduction of the effective area from which the gas may emanate. Also, with such increment comes the potential of the attack of anodes by ion such Chloride ion or even hydroxide ions if the electrolyte is enhanced with a base. Since in this project was done in a short interval of time such extreme detrimental effects as a result of these possibilities did not occur.

Al anode setup experience the most degradation in terms of its anode as a weight loss of about 20% its weigh over the just about two hours of electrolysis with 4M NaCl electrolyte run-other anodes in Zn and tin basically maintained their weight when measure on the balance. However, zinc especially producing high current density is expected to lose the most weight. This may point to the fact that Al may have morphology that tend to make it dissolve in the electrolytic process but not feature in the production of electrons.

Also, for the all the anodes considered in the various anode-electrolytic cells, there was gas production (in at the cathode). However, Al anode electrolytic cell was the only setup that produced gas at the anode (Oxygen evolution reaction). Aluminium, with reduction potential of about -1.7V is the most reactive of all the anode used according to electrochemical series. This could have played a role in the ensuring that oxygen evolution occurred at the anode. Yet this reactive ability seems not to have helped in making hydrogen production higher in Al setup that in Zn setup. This maybe because the hybrid reaction in Zn setup makes the use of energy more efficient than in Al setup as suggested by (Sun et al., 2021, Chen et al., 2022).

6 Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 conclusion

The current densities achieved by the application of the voltage in an electrolysis setup is an important parameter as it influences the amount of hydrogen produced. A very efficient electrolytic system is one that yields the maximum current density with a set voltage. While the current densities of three metals (Zn, Sn and Al) as anodes in the different electrolytic setups were relatively low compared to industrial scale electrolyzers, Zn-anode electrolytic cells generate the highest current density based on equal benchmarks of concentration and voltage. It could even perform better with unequal benchmarks. For example, Sn-electrolytic cells recording the lowest value of gas production, required at least 400mV of overpotential to achieve a current density achieved by zinc at 1.6V. Al-cells also required some overpotential but a considerably small amount.

Given that faradaic efficiency of each of the three anode-electrolytic cells hover around 90%, the current densities were directly translated into high hydrogen output rates. The Zn-anode system is thus clearly the winner in hydrogen production with a hydrogen production rate of $1.12 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol/scm}^2$ while Sn-anode systems have the lowest value of $7.6 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mol/scm}^2$.

However, alternate reactions to oxygen evolution reactions observed in the Zn-anode and Sn-anode systems that produced precipitates, albeit not quantified, lead to a challenge. This formation could hamper daily operations of electrolyzers with such anodes especially if the electrolysis goes on for a long period. This situation could impact operational expenditure if remedies such as pH regulation are to be used.

The zinc anode is thus the anode of choice among the three for high production of hydrogen. The concentration increases of electrolyte, from 1M to 4M, used in the electrolysis increased indicators such as the current density and subsequently hydrogen production rate. But an increase in pH of 4M electrolyte to pH of 12, used for Zn anode systems, could not generate much higher current densities and may have even been counterproductive.

The effect of increasing PH value for the 4M electrolyte in the Zn-anode system did not elicit the any increment current density and hydrogen production-even worse. That said the values were similar, and it may suffice to say that mass limitation for current production may have been reached for the 4M electrolyte for the voltages used.

Also, hybrid nature of an electrolysis may contribute to high current densities, but this may depend to an extent on the electrochemical characteristics of the anode chosen as well. Even though Sn anode system also experience hybrid electrolysis as Zn anode system, its current density and hydrogen output were not as high as Al. Zn was the best performer.

6.2 Recommendations

A study could be conducted on the effect of alternate reaction in hybrid electrolysis and its impact on the long-term operation of electrolyzers.

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